

PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS FOR ORGANIZING ADDITIONAL SERVICES IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS.

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Abstract: The article comprehensively covers the pedagogical conditions for organizing additional services in preschool educational organizations.

Аннотация: В статье всесторонне освещены педагогические условия организации дополнительных услуг в дошкольных образовательных учреждениях.

Keywords: innovative environment, preschool education, management development, educational technologies, creativity, spatial organization

Ключевые слова: инновационная среда, дошкольное образование, развитие менеджмента, образовательные технологии, творчество, организация пространства.

In our republic, special attention is paid to the introduction and development of alternative forms of education and upbringing, state support for the development of preschool education and upbringing, as well as the introduction of modern innovative and information and communication technologies for the comprehensive development of preschool children. The law emphasizes the importance of state guarantees for the receipt of preschool education and upbringing by every child, including children with special educational needs, and establishes requirements for the organization of the educational process in preschool educational organizations.

Today, it is important to study the characteristics of financial relations, which are one of the economic foundations of the organization and management of the activities of budget-financed institutions, and especially preschool educational organizations, which are considered important links in the continuous education system, and to clarify the mechanism for financing the costs of preschool educational organizations.

Also, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-3261 dated September 9, 2017 "On measures to radically improve the preschool education system" indicates the existing systemic shortcomings and reasons that hinder the full implementation of state policy in the field of preschool education, in particular:

firstly, the current state of preschool education management does not allow for the timely identification and elimination of systemic problems, the development and introduction of modern innovative technologies in this area, including in the non-state sector;

secondly, public-private partnership mechanisms aimed at attracting investments in the field of preschool education, including the establishment of socially inclusive preschool educational organizations, their material and technical reequipment, and the use of advanced pedagogical technologies, have not been introduced;

Thirdly, the current state of the infrastructure and material and technical base of preschool educational organizations does not allow ensuring full coverage of children by

preschool educational organizations, and the growth of the country's population is leading to overcrowding of some preschool educational organizations;

Fourthly, the preparation of educational and methodological, didactic (including games and toys) materials and fiction that reflect national cultural and historical values and arouse interest in reading from childhood, and the introduction into the activities of preschool educational organizations, do not meet modern requirements;

Fifthly, the current system of training and retraining of personnel cannot provide the preschool education sector with highly qualified specialists capable of professionally solving the issues of raising and comprehensive development of children;

Sixthly, the low level of the system of material incentives for employees of preschool educational organizations does not allow attracting qualified personnel;

Seventh, shortcomings in the organization of the work of territorial health authorities in providing medical services to children in preschool educational organizations lead to a decrease in the effectiveness of preventive measures to protect the life and health of children, including ensuring healthy nutrition. According to the resolution, a commission was established to critically study the preschool education system and develop proposals for its further improvement, and its main tasks include the following:

- review state requirements for organizing high-quality preschool education, taking into account advanced foreign experience in the field of harmonious development of preschool children;
- prepare proposals for introducing a simplified procedure for licensing the activities of non-state preschool educational organizations, improving their organizational and legal forms, having studied existing practice and advanced foreign experience.

Today, the educational process in preschool educational organizations is being enriched with modern educational programs, and cooperation in creating conditions for the intellectual, moral, aesthetic and physical development of children is bearing fruit. It is planned to implement a number of measures in order to further expand the scope of work in this area.

The organization of additional services in preschool educational institutions requires an integrated approach based on clearly defined principles and methods. These approaches should take into account the specific characteristics of preschool age, ensure high quality of the educational process, and meet the needs of children and their parents.

The scientific study of researcher G.F. Ksendzova presents the results of studying the organization of management in a preschool educational institution in a market economy.

A similar idea was expressed by O.M. Svalova in her scientific research, which is aimed at developing and analyzing the theoretical foundations of the organization of pedagogical marketing and identifying the necessary pedagogical conditions for effective management of marketing of educational services in preschool educational organizations.

In our opinion, it is important to adhere to certain scientifically based principles for the effective organization of additional services in preschool educational organizations. These principles are aimed at improving the quality of services, their development and creating the most favorable conditions for children and their parents. The main principles and their essence are described in detail below.

Indivduallashtirish tamoyili		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Bolalarning individualligi va rivojlanish darajasini baholash uchun maxsus diagnostik metodlar joriy etish. ➤ Differensial yondashuv asosida mashg'ulotlarni tashkil qilish. ➤ O'zlashtirish darajasiga qarab, mos dasturlar ishlab chiqish.
Ixtiyoriylik tamoyili		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Ota-onalarning xizmatlarga bo'lgan talabini aniqlash maqsadida so'rovnomalarni o'tkazish. ➤ Bolalarga turli xizmat turlarini sinab ko'rish imkoniyatini yaratish (masalan, bepul sinov darslari).
Integrativ yondashuv tamoyili		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Qo'shimcha xizmatlarni asosiy o'quv jarayoni bilan uyg'un holda tashkil qilish. ➤ Turli yo'nalishlar bo'yicha qo'shimcha mashg'ulotlarni kombinatsiyalash (masalan, san'at darslarini mantiqiy o'yinlar bilan birlashtirish).
Sifat tamoyili		<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Xizmatlarni amalga oshiruvchi pedagoglar va mutaxassislarning doimiy malakasini oshirish. 2. Qo'shimcha xizmatlarni baholash tizimini ishlab chiqish (ota-onalar va pedagoglar fikrini o'rganish).
Modullilik tamoyili		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Mashg'ulotlarni turli darajalarga ajratish (boshlang'ich, o'rta va ilg'or bosqichlar). ➤ Ota-onalarga moslashuvchan ta'lim dasturlarini tanlash imkoniyatini berish.
Tashqi va ichki resurslardan samarali foydalanish tamoyili		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalar va innovatsion metodlarni joriy etish. ➤ Xizmatlarni tashkil etishda xususiy sektor va jamoatchilik tashkilotlari bilan hamkorlikni yo'lga qo'yish. ➤ Resurslardan samarali foydalanish uchun reja asosida taqsimot

Social competence is not only the effective organization of one's own activities, but also the simultaneous engagement in additional activities. A socially competent teacher knows how to work in collaboration;

Personal competence is such a teacher who does not tire of self-development and self-expression. He is an example with his own ideas, research, plans, independent decision-making, ability to work with information and work on himself;

A.K. Mapkova also includes the subjective characteristics of a specialist in the content of the concept of professional competence and further expands this concept. In the views of psychologist A.K. Mapkova, a person achieves high results only when all the qualities are formed in a person and they are used during his professional activity. In her opinion, the concept of professional competence is such labor activity of a specialist that results in high-level professional activity and the specialist manifests himself as a person.

Individual competence is knowledge of self-management methods, preparation for professional development and the ability to create professional innovations. At the same time,

the owner of this competence is distinguished by his interest in enriching his knowledge with innovations, acquiring psychological and pedagogical knowledge.

P.Kh. Tugushev in his research bases competence not only as a master of his work, but also notes that he must correctly and rationally organize work, systematically understand and solve all problems related to his activity. According to its basis, competence is not measured only by skills, but also includes such qualities as the ability to correctly set a task, to find a rational solution when faced with specific problems. Such a person deserves the title of a competent person in a particular field.

N.V. Kukhapev, on the other hand, justified the dependence of pedagogical competence on the concept of pedagogical skills as a set of specific qualities arising from the psychological and pedagogical preparation of the pedagogical person and the most effective way to solve pedagogical problems.

N.Yu. Postalyuk, T.C. Pepekrestova emphasize that "Professional competence is a set of knowledge and all ethical rules necessary in the process of activity."

V.A. Slastenin assesses "Professional competence" as the degree to which a person has mastered his professional activity and defines it as follows:

- attitude to this activity, need and interest in it, aspirations, values, purpose of activity, perception of his social place;
- assessment of his personal identity and position as a specialist, professional knowledge, skills and abilities, other characteristics specific to the profession;
- ability to manage his professional formation and growth on this basis, etc.

In psychology, N.E. Shupkova, E.A. Klimov, N.V. Kuzmina interpret competence as qualities and abilities that help to solve various situations and problems that arise in life.

Professional competence is compliance with the rules of a particular profession, as well as the set of innovations, knowledge and abilities necessary during the activity and their interaction with the environment.

In our opinion, the issue of organizing and managing innovative services in preschool educational organizations is one of the priority areas of today's educational policy. We believe that the development of innovative forms of pedagogical services not only increases the efficiency of the educational process, but also serves to create favorable conditions for the comprehensive development of children.

Based on the analysis of scientific sources, it can be said that educational services are an important factor in the socialization of the child, the development of his abilities and the formation of independent thinking skills. Therefore, the innovative organization of pedagogical services should also be at the center of management activities.

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